

Utilizing Snake Rescue Data to Understand Snake Distribution Pattern and Human-Snake Conflict in Pakur Forest Division, Jharkhand India

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to utilize data from voluntary snake rescue operations conducted between May 2022 and May 2025 to understand the diversity, distribution patterns, and human-snake conflict (HSC) dynamics in the Pakur Forest Division, Jharkhand. A total of 130 individuals belonging to 20 snake species across 5 families were rescued, including 5 venomous, 2 mildly venomous, and 13 non-venomous species. Most rescues occurred in human-dominated landscapes, particularly during the monsoon season, aligning with increased snake movement and breeding activity. Notably, species such as the Spectacled Cobra, Common Krait, and Russell's Viper were among the most frequently encountered and pose significant risk to rural and Urban populations. Despite the dominance of non-venomous species, lack of awareness leads to their indiscriminate killing due to fear and misidentification. The study emphasizes the urgent need for awareness programs on snake conservation, safe coexistence, and first-aid practices. It also highlights the necessity of ensuring the availability of anti-venom in Primary Health Centers (PHCs) and dispensaries for effective snakebite treatment. Findings from this research not only reflect the ecological significance of the region's Herpetofauna but also serve as a foundation for planning community-based conservation and conflict mitigation strategies.

Keywords: Pakur Forest Division, Human-Snake Conflict, Herpetofaunal Diversity

INTRODUCTION

Snakes are an integral part of the ecosystems in which they operate and are related to humans in direct as well as indirect ways. Snakes play a significant role by feeding on a wide range of animals. At the same time, they also serve as prey to other animals. Snakes, commonly known as the friends of farmers, serve as natural predators of rodent pests that pose a threat to agricultural fields. In India, the snake fauna is extremely diverse and rich (Vyas, 2013). It is home to over 270 species of snakes, including 60 venomous (Whitakar and Captain 2008). Unfortunately, due to insufficient knowledge and awareness among the population and farmers, these snakes are often killed without recognizing their vital role (Bharath *et al.*, 2021). Snakes, unlike most wild animals, are more likely to share the living space with humans in rural and urban landscapes alike, in extremely close proximity. Notably, some of these snake species are

potentially dangerous to humans. Close encounters of humans with snakes are, for the most part, inevitable, as these animals (including venomous species) have successfully adapted to live close to human habitations that provide easy prey. These species are either pulled into such habitations in search of prey or are pushed out of natural habitats due to fragmentation and destruction of the same (MoEF&CC 2023).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Area:

The study was conducted in Pakur Forest Division. It is located at (23°40" N to 25°18" N latitude and 86°25" E to 87°57" E longitude) (Fig. 1). Spreads over an area of 92.88 sq. km. Pakur Forest Division is situated entirely within the Pakur District in the north-eastern portion of Santhal Pargana in Jharkhand. The forests of Pakur Division comprise of 14.43 sq. km. of Reserved Forests, 57.60 sq. km. of Protected Forests

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and 20.84 sq. km. of Unclassed Forests. Administratively, the forests of Pakur Division are split into 3 Forest Ranges namely- Pakur (7.15 sq. km.), Hiranpur (50.06 sq. km.) and Amrapar (35.66 sq. km.) (Sharma, 2016). Pakur is predominantly a hilly area with certain pockets of plain land. Topographically it is divided into three parts i.e. the hilly area, the rolling area and alluvial area. The hilly area includes the whole of Damini-i-koh from northern corner of Pakur district up to the south-west bordering the Birbhum district of West Bengal. A narrow continuous strip of alluvial soil which lies between the Ganga feeder canal and the loop line of Eastern Railway is very fertile. The rest of the part covers the Rolling areas, which is less conducive for agriculture (Sharma, 2016). Average altitude of the division is about 300 meters above MSL. There are three main rivers in this division namely, Bansloi, Torai & Brahmini. Rivers Bansloi & Torai flow in the middle while Brahmini flows in the Southern portion of the division. The division is characterized by three distinct seasons – summer, rainy and winter. The summers are extremely hot and last from March to

May with maximum temperature rising up to 42 to 46 °C in some places. The winters are cold and last from November to February with minimum temperature going around 3 °C. The average annual rainfall is about 1354.60 mm. According to the classification of forest types of India, the forests of Pakur forest Division fall into Northern Dry Peninsular Sal Forest– 5B/C-1 type, Northern Tropical Dry Mixed Deciduous Forest– 5B/C-2 type and Tropical Dry Deciduous Scrub Forest–5B/DS-1 type (Champion and Seth 1968). The forest is mainly dominated by *Shorea robusta* trees and their associates namely- *Terminalia chebula*, *Buchanania lanzan*, *Semicarpus anacardium*, etc. along with occasional bamboo brakes. These forests of entire Santhal Parganas (which now include the districts of Pakur, Godda, Sahibganj, Dumka and Jamtara) were rich in wildlife at the turn of the 20th century, within the next few decades' large mammalian fauna was wiped off due to rampant hunting and habitat loss. Birdlife is rich in these forests. (https://forest.jharkhand.gov.in/know-your-division_pakur.aspx).

Fig. 1. Map of the study area.

METHODOLOGY:

Snakes were voluntarily rescued as per information received from the inhabitants and local people of the

division for a period of three years from May 2022-May 2025. Falcon 6 Feet Yellow & Black Snake Catcher Stick (FPSC-66) was used to catch the snakes. Snakes were rescued without hurting and

were immediately kept in snake bags or PVC pipe encased with cloth or other safe containers with holes to supply enough air for survival inside the enclosure and then released as early as possible. The detailed information during the rescue operations from different parts of Pakur forest division were noted down including the information of date and time of rescue, details of the area, species name of the snake that is rescued including details about whether the snake is venomous, mildly venomous or non-venomous etc. Sighted individuals were captured on camera and checked out for further information. Special care was taken so that no species get injured or stressed during rescue processes. None of the

individuals were kept as samples, and after collecting data, they were released into natural habitat i.e., to the nearby forest areas. Daniel (2002) and Whitaker (2006)'s field guides and books were used for accurate identification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A total number of 20 species of snakes from 5 families were rescued during the study period out of which 5 species belonging to 2 families were venomous, 2 species was mildly venomous and 13 species belonging to 3 families were non-venomous (Table 1).

Banded Karait	Banded Kukri	Banded Racer	Green Vine Snake
Black Headed Royal Snake	Common Sad Boa	Russell's Viper	Common wolf Snake (mutant)
Common Bronze-Back Tree Snake	Common Karait	Checkered Keelback	Monocled Cobra

Fig. 2. Some of the rescued and released snakes from Pakur forest division.

Table 1: Preliminary checklist of snake diversity from Pakur Forest Division, basically encountered during the rescue initiatives

Sr. No.	Common name	Scientific name	Family	Category	Distribution in Division
1	Banded Krait	<i>Bungarus fasciatus</i> (Schneider, 1801)	Elapidae	Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
2	Banded Kukri	<i>Oligodon arnensis</i> (Shaw, 1802)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
3	Banded Racer	<i>Lycodon fasciolatus</i> (Shaw, 1802)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
4	Barred Wolf Snake	<i>Lycodon striatus</i> (Shaw, 1802)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Amrapara Block (Amrapara Range)
5	Black Headed Royal Snake	<i>Spalerosophis atriceps</i> (Fischer, 1885)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
6	Brahminy Blind Snake	<i>Indotyphlops braminus</i> (Daudin, 1803)	Typhlopidae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
7	Buff Striped keelback	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
8	Checkered Keelback	<i>Fowlea piscator</i> (Schneider, 1799)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
9	Common Bronze-Back Tree Snake	<i>Dendrelaphis tristis</i> (Daudin, 1803)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
10	Common Krait	<i>Bungarus caeruleus</i> (Schneider, 1801)	Elapidae	Venomous	Whole Division
11	Common Kukri snake	<i>Oligodon arnensis</i> (Shaw, 1802)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
12	Common Sand Boa	<i>Eryx conicus</i> (Schneider, 1801)	Boidae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division

13	Common Wolf Snake	<i>Lycodon capucinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
14	Forsten's Cat Snake	<i>Boiga forsteni</i> (Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
15	Green Vine Snake	<i>Ahaetulla nasuta</i> (Bonnaterre, 1790)	Colubridae	Mild Venomous	Maheshpur & Pakur Block (Pakur Range)
16	Indian Rat Snake	<i>Ptyas mucosa</i> (Blyth, 1854)	Colubridae	Non-Venomous	Whole Division
17	Monocled Cobra	<i>Naja kaouthia</i> (Lesson, 1831)	Elapidae	Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
18	Ornate Flying Snake	<i>Chrysopelea ornata ornatissima</i> (Werner, 1925)	Colubridae	Mild Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
19	Russell's Viper	<i>Daboia russelii</i> (Shaw & Nodder, 1797)	Viperidae	Venomous	Maheshpur Block (Pakur Range)
20	Spectacled Cobra	<i>Naja naja</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Elapidae	Venomous	Whole Division

Five species namely- *Naja naja*, *Naja kaouthia*, *Daboia russelii*, *Ptyas mucosa* and *Fowlea piscator* belonged to Schedule-I category. The rest of the fifteen species belonged to Schedule-II category of (The Wildlife (Protection) Amendment Act, 2022). As per IUCN, 2001 (Version 3.1) one species *Oligodon arnensis* belonged to Vulnerable (VN) category while the rest of the species rescued

belonged to Least Concern (LC) category. The result indicates that 65% of snake species were non-venomous, but once they appear in public place, residential areas or in the agriculture fields they were killed by local people. On very few occasions, the people who were aware of the importance and conservation of snakes informed the snake friends, and the species was saved (table 1).

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of IWPA 2022 status of snake species found during rescue initiatives from Pakur Forest Division.

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of venom category of snake species found during rescue initiatives from Pakur Forest Division.

It has been observed that the major habitats preferred by snakes in the Pakur and Maheshpur beats was human-dominated areas. A total of 97 snakes were rescued from these two regions. Among the species rescued during the study, the Spectacled Cobra, Common Krait, Indian Rat Snake, Checkered Keelback, Common Sand Boa, Common Wolf Snake, and Common Kukri were found throughout the year across all seasons. Russell's Viper was mainly active from August to June, with reduced activity and rare sightings during the remaining months. Seasonal trends revealed that species like the Monocled Cobra, Ornate Flying Snake, Buff-striped Keelback, Green Vine Snake, Bronze-backed Tree Snake, and Forsten's Cat Snake were rescued predominantly during the monsoon season (June to September). Overall, most snake rescues during the study occurred in the monsoon season, which also coincides with the hatching period and increased prey availability, explaining the presence of juvenile and young snakes. On average, 1–2 snake rescue incidents per week were done by Pakur forest department from residential areas in both towns and villages in the entire division. In total, 130 snakes were rescued from the study area. The most commonly encountered species included the Spectacled Cobra, Common Wolf Snake, Common Krait, Russell's Viper, Common Sand Boa, Common Kukri Snake, Banded Kukri, and Banded Racer. These species are predominantly nocturnal and are typically encountered at night, whereas diurnal species such as the Indian Rat Snake, Checkered Keelback, Buff-striped Keelback, Green Keelback, and Worm Snakes were often spotted during the day

by local residents. The abundance of snake species varies both spatially and temporally. Juvenile snakes—those recently hatched and yet to establish a territory—are naturally more abundant than adults. Additionally, generalist and highly adaptable species tend to be more prevalent than habitat specialists. The distribution and population density of snakes also differ across landscapes and habitat types, depending on each species' ability to adapt to rapidly changing environments. Under natural conditions, snakes are secretive and are usually encountered randomly or accidentally, particularly when their microhabitats are disturbed by human activities such as earth-moving, construction, and farming. In rural areas, snakes are frequently found resting in warm and concealed places like piles of fuelwood, cow dung, bricks, or stones, which provide safe and thermally favorable microhabitats. Temporally, snake encounters peak during the rainy season, when they emerge from burrows and other shelters due to flooding or increased humidity. Human habitations often attract snakes during this period, offering warmth, shelter, nesting sites, and easy access to prey such as rodents, making these areas favorable for overwintering or egg-laying. Venomous species exhibit habitat preferences: for instance, Russell's Viper, the Spectacled (Binocellate) Cobra, and the Common Krait favor dry environments, while the Monocellate Cobra and Banded Krait prefer moist, swampy areas, wetlands, and water-logged habitats. Based on activity patterns, snakes can be broadly classified as diurnal, nocturnal, or crepuscular. However, most human-snake conflict occurs outside the typical

activity periods of these reptiles, often due to accidental encounters. In natural ecosystems, interspecies competition among snakes for food and territory exists, often resulting in avoidance behavior. This study highlights the effectiveness of utilizing snake rescue data as a proxy to understand the spatio-temporal distribution of snakes and assess the intensity and patterns of human-snake conflict (HSC) in the Pakur Forest Division. The consistent rescue of 20 different snake species, including venomous, mildly venomous, and non-venomous types across varied habitats, emphasizes the division's rich Herpetofauna diversity and the ecological value of its landscapes. The high frequency of rescues from human-dominated landscapes, particularly in the Pakur and Maheshpur beats, indicates that snakes are increasingly occupying peri-urban and rural areas due to habitat disturbance, prey abundance, and favourable microhabitats. Seasonal patterns show that most rescues and human-snake encounters occurred during the monsoon season—coinciding with increased snake activity due to flooding of burrows, breeding, and prey movement. Such interactions often result in snakebite incidents, especially when venomous species such as the Spectacled Cobra, Common Krait, Russell's Viper, and Monocled Cobra enter homes, farms, or fuelwood storage areas. A significant observation was that despite 65% of the rescued species being non-venomous, they were often killed due to fear and misidentification. This underscores a critical gap in local awareness and highlights the urgent need for **community education and awareness programs** focusing on snake identification, ecological roles, and safe behaviour during encounters. Educating schoolchildren, farmers, and rural households through visual aids, rescue demonstrations, and campaigns can greatly reduce fear-driven killings and snakebite incidents. Given the presence of highly venomous species in the division, the study also emphasizes the **urgent need to ensure the availability of anti-venom in all Primary Health Centres (PHCs) and local dispensaries**. Timely medical intervention following a snakebite can significantly reduce mortality and long-term complications. However, the lack of accessible healthcare infrastructure and delayed treatment remains a major challenge in rural Jharkhand. Strengthening the rural health system with anti-venom stock, trained healthcare professionals,

and snakebite management protocols is imperative for minimizing fatalities. Moreover, interspecies interactions—such as competition for prey between Rat Snakes and Cobras—and the habitat preferences of different species provide valuable insights into their behavioural ecology. Understanding these patterns helps in planning habitat management and rescue response strategies. The presence of species listed under Schedule I of the Wildlife Protection Act (1972, amended 2022) and those categorized as "Vulnerable" by the IUCN adds further conservation significance to the study.

CONCLUSIONS:

Biodiversity is a vital asset to humanity, and its conservation is essential for sustaining ecological balance and ensuring the well-being of future generations. The recorded diversity of snake species in the Pakur Forest Division, captured solely through rescue operations—indicates a rich and ecologically significant Herpetofauna habitat. Such diversity not only highlights the presence of a healthy ecosystem but also suggests the existence of a well-structured food web supported by organisms across various trophic levels. The regular presence of a wide range of snake species in human-influenced landscapes, including educational campuses, underscores the adaptability of these reptiles and the urgency of reconciling human-snake coexistence. Unfortunately, widespread misconceptions and fear often lead to the unnecessary killing of snakes, including harmless and ecologically beneficial species. This study reinforces the importance of snakes in maintaining ecological harmony, particularly through their role in controlling rodent populations and balancing prey-predator dynamics. It also demonstrates that snake rescues, when carried out ethically and systematically, can be a valuable tool for both conservation and public education. The findings serve as a strong foundation for community-based mitigation strategies for human-snake conflict (HSC), especially in rural and semi-urban settings. Considering this, it is imperative to strengthen awareness programs, encourage coexistence through education, and promote further scientific research to deepen our understanding of the region's snake diversity.

FUTURE SCOPE:

We aim to continue our voluntary snake rescue operations within the division and surrounding areas to the best of our capacity. Our efforts will also focus on raising awareness among local communities, encouraging them not to panic at the sight of a snake, as most species are non-aggressive unless provoked or threatened. The observation of such significant species diversity through rescue operations alone indicates the presence of rich Herpetofauna biodiversity in the region. This highlights the need for more intensive and systematic studies to comprehensively document the Herpetofauna of the Pakur Forest Division. Additionally, there is an urgent need to ensure that anti-venom is readily available at all Primary Health Centers (PHCs) and nearby dispensaries to provide timely and effective treatment in case of snakebite incidents. Strengthening the healthcare response and building awareness on snakebite prevention and first-aid can greatly reduce snakebite-related mortality and fear-driven killing of snakes in the region.

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